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Identifying gaps and data inconsistencies
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New methodology for facilitating the food wastage quantification. Identifying gaps and data inconsistencies

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Highlights

- It identifies the potential food-waste generation at local and supra-local scale.
- It presents a visual tool for decision making in issues related to food waste.
- It generates a comparative framework between different municipalities.
- It contributes to the detection of gaps and inconsistencies of data reported in previous studies.

Abstract

This work aims at providing a new methodology to facilitate the process of quantifying the food waste according to European standards all along the agrifood chain combining information that is becoming available at local level.

The baseline data needed is taken from the Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community (NACE), particularly with the more disaggregated level called “classes”. This information has been combined with data from the trading income tax at municipal scale thanks to the use of the Geographic Information Systems (GIS) and the common codes for NACE classes, generating a visual tool for the localization of points with high potential food-waste generation.

The result is an intuitive and easy to use methodology that simplify the decision making process in order to quantify the potential focus of food waste at local level. Thanks to the use of this methodology, it is possible to geographically identify the potential food waste-generation focus at municipal scale. Furthermore, it is possible to identify all economic activities which could generate food surpluses, classified according to stages of the agrifood chain at local level. Furthermore, the methodology will be easily replicable throughout the European Union at the municipal scale.

This new methodology generates straightforward and easy-to-interpret results for the decision making process in the framework of the quantification of the food waste at local and supralocal scale and it provides adequate procedures which are easy adaptable to the specific circumstances in each municipality. Moreover, this method could have applications for larger territorial contexts, as the national scale, detecting possible points for improvement of the current official figures at this respect.

Keywords

Food waste, food losses, quantification methodology, food wastage, waste quantification, agrifood chain

Introduction

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of United Nations report, roughly one-third of food produced for human consumption is lost or wasted globally, which amounts to about 1.3 billion tons per year [1].

The negative impacts of the global food waste problem are not only related to the reduced availability and consumption of food, but also are directly involved in environmental impacts such as greenhouse gas emissions, consumption of surface and groundwater resources and land occupation [2].

Food wastage occurs at different stages of the food value chain: production, post-production procedures, processing, distribution, and consumption [3]. The methodology for estimating the food wastage at the global scale is referred as a “macro-approach” [4]. This approach is based on a comparison of inputs and outputs using mass or energy balances.

According to current estimations [5], approximately a 63 per cent increase of crop calories is required from 9,500 trillion kcal per year in 2006 to 15,500 trillion kcal in 2050 in order to assure of adequate calories in all regions around the world.

Thus, thanks to the reduction of the current food loss and waste, it is possible to improve food availability without increasing the agricultural land and the environmental impacts associated to it.

This social and environment problem has been further emphasized by the European Parliament [6] and the challenge of food waste measurement and of quantification was also addressed within the framework of the European Union [7] where the food waste figures at national level were published.

These data have served as the starting point for those Member States which have no studies regarding the food waste at national level. However, the European Court of Auditors puts into question the effectiveness provided for by European rules. It includes the target to halve the food waste per capita by 2030 throughout the agrifood chain [8, 9] because there is no a base year defined in order to set the reduction target for 2030 [10].

This lack of information at national level was also expressed in the European project called FUSIONS [11] where it is possible to identify significant differences between European Union Member States in terms of the availability of information about food waste at national level:

Country	1. Production (NACE 1-3)	2. Processing (NACE 10-11)	3. Wholesale and logistics (NACE 46)	4. Retail and markets (NACE 47)	5. Redistribution (food donation etc.)	6. Food service (NACE 56)	7. Household
Austria	Red	Yellow	Red	Green	Yellow	Green	Green
Belgium	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow
Bulgaria	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Croatia	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow
Cyprus	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Czech republic	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow
Denmark	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green
Estonia	Red	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow
Finland	Green	Green	Red	Yellow	Red	Green	Green
France	Green	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Green	Yellow
Germany	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green
Greece	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow
Hungary	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Ireland	Red	Red	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Green	Green
Italy	Green	Green	Green	Green	Red	Yellow	Yellow
Latvia	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Lithuania	Yellow	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow
Luxembourg	Red	Yellow	Green	Green	Red	Yellow	Green
Malta	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Green
Netherlands	Red	Red	Red	Green	Yellow	Yellow	Green
Poland	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Portugal	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Red	Red
Romania	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Slovakia	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Yellow	Red	Yellow	Yellow
Slovenia	Red	Red	Green	Green	Red	Yellow	Yellow
Spain	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red	Red
Sweden	Green	Yellow	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green
United Kingdom	Yellow	Green	Green	Green	Red	Green	Green

Figure 1 Countries Providing Data. FUSIONS.
In red “no data available” / Yellow “low quality” / Green “sufficient quality”

Those countries that contain information designated as “sufficient quality” (green colour) are fundamentally linked to the existence of national reports carried out to have the food waste figures in their own countries. The remaining countries generally publish as official figures the information provided in the above-mentioned report by the European Commission [7] which usually come from estimates with certain gaps and inconsistencies.

The quantification methods used to measure the food waste issue at national scale is called as a “micro approach”. This approach uses sample data regarding specific agrifood chain actors. Within the micro approach, there is no single method to measure the food waste issue along the entire food chain, but there a wide variety of methodologies which could be used [12].

The group of methods was incorporated into the recommendations by FUSIONS on quantitative techniques to estimate the level of wasted food across EU-28 [13]. Moreover, one of the main conclusions was the

importance of the harmonization of results between countries, sectors and steps in the food supply chain. For this purpose, FUSIONS recommended the use of the codes from the Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community (NACE).

Inside classification of NACE, there are different categories and levels established according to the greater or lesser degree of specificity of the economic activities. FUSIONS suggested using the more specific digit code if possible [14]. These recommendations may represent a step forward for dealing with the current difficulty to compare food waste studies. They are normally adapted to their specific objective, focus only on certain steps along the agrifood chain and use different data and methodologies to measure the current food waste.

At local level, the situation is quite similar despite the existence of a similar action protocol to quantify the food waste at this scale [15]. Despite the fact that this protocol is ample and robust, visual tools might be required in order to facilitate the implementation of the procedures and build an enabling framework for decision making within the general course of action to gather data from the food waste at municipal scale.

While this protocol allows a high degree of flexibility for adapting to different geographic scales and case studies. Thus, the contribution of the geographic component, for example through visual tools, to facilitate decision making processes defining the location of potential focus of food waste might be a step in the right direction towards quantifying the current food waste to certain spatial categories, such as the municipal level. Furthermore, the definition of what entities should be made part of the identification of the generating sources of food waste could avoid certain gaps and lacks of definition in the process of quantifying and thereby preventing the possibility of these gaps may result in inactions in relation to tackling the food waste problem.

In addition, this methodology helps assess the representativeness of the data about food waste at local level previously obtained, and it allows for the development of a comparative framework between different municipalities. Furthermore, it can be useful to identify possible gaps and inconsistencies in official data published at national level.

Methodology

The proposed methodology is based on the classification of Statistical Classification of Economic Activities in the European Community (NACE), where different categories are divided into sections, divisions, groups and classes (see Figure 2):

Division	Group	Class	ISIC Rev. 4	
SECTION A — AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FISHING				
01		Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities		
	01.1		Growing of non-perennial crops	
		01.11	Growing of cereals (except rice), leguminous crops and oil seeds	0111
		01.12	Growing of rice	0112
		01.13	Growing of vegetables and melons, roots and tubers	0113
		01.14	Growing of sugar cane	0114
		01.15	Growing of tobacco	0115
		01.16	Growing of fibre crops	0116
		01.19	Growing of other non-perennial crops	0119
		01.2		Growing of perennial crops
	01.21		Growing of grapes	0121
	01.22		Growing of tropical and subtropical fruits	0122
	01.23		Growing of citrus fruits	0123
	01.24		Growing of pome fruits and stone fruits	0124
	01.25		Growing of other tree and bush fruits and nuts	0125
	01.26		Growing of oleaginous fruits	0126
	01.27		Growing of beverage crops	0127
	01.28		Growing of spices, aromatic, drug and pharmaceutical crops	0128
	01.29		Growing of other perennial crops	0129
	01.3		Plant propagation	
01.30		Plant propagation	0130	
01.4		Animal production		
	01.41	Raising of dairy cattle	0141*	
	01.42	Raising of other cattle and buffaloes	0141*	
	01.43	Raising of horses and other equines	0142	
	01.44	Raising of camels and camelids	0143	

Figure 2 Example of the detailed structure of NACE.

Thus, those categories, which could potentially generate food surpluses, have been defined and broken down in classes. In this manner, it avoids referring to higher categories, as has been the case in previous studies [7]. The main drawback of these previous analyses is the possibility of including data regarding economic activities which could potentially generate food surpluses not intended for human consumption.

Taking into account the classes proposed by NACE, three types of situations have been distinguished:

- Potential Food-Generation Surpluses. Commercial activities defined by the official EUROSTAT document [16] that might be susceptible to generate food surpluses.
- Non-Potential Food-Generation Surpluses. Commercial activities that cannot be susceptible to generate food surpluses.
- In-situ Verification. Commercial activities that may occasionally produce food-generation surpluses and others with non-potential food generation. For this reason, it is necessary to verify in-situ the concrete economic activity linked with the specific case and its relation with the agrifood value chain.

Section	Division	Group	Class	ISIC Rev. 4		
SECTION A — AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FISHING	01 Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities	01,1 Growing of non-perennial crops	01,11	Growing of cereals (except rice), leguminous crops and oil seeds	0111	
			01,12	Growing of rice	0112	
			01,13	Growing of vegetables and melons, roots and tubers	0113	
			01,14	Growing of sugar cane	0114	
			01,15	Growing of tobacco	0115	
			01,16	Growing of fibre crops	0116	
			01,19	Growing of other non-perennial crops	0119	
			01,2 Growing of perennial crops	01,21	Growing of grapes	0121
				01,22	Growing of tropical and subtropical fruits	0122
		01,23		Growing of citrus fruits	0123	
		01,24		Growing of pome fruits and stone fruits	0124	
		01,25		Growing of other tree and bush fruits and nuts	0125	
		01,26		Growing of oleaginous fruits	0126	
		01,27		Growing of beverage crops	0127	
		01,28		Growing of spices, aromatic, drug and pharmaceutical crops	0128	
		01,29	Growing of other perennial crops	0129		
		01,3 Plant propagation	01,30	Plant propagation	0130	
		01,4 Animal production	01,41	Raising of dairy cattle	0141*	
			01,42	Raising of other cattle and buffaloes	0141*	
			01,43	Raising of horses and other equines	0142	
01,44	Raising of camels and camelids		0143			
01,45	Raising of sheep and goats		0144			
01,46	Raising of swine/pigs		0145			
01,47	Raising of poultry		0146			
01,49	Raising of other animals		0149			
01,5 Mixed farming	01,50	Mixed farming	0150			

Potential Food-Generation Surpluses

No Potential Food-Generation Surpluses

In-Situ Verification

Figure 3 and 4 Example of the detailed structure of NACE, identifying the different types of classes in accordance with their potentiality as a food surpluses generator

After defining all classes from NACE, under one of the three typologies stated above: Potential Food-Generation Surpluses, Non-Potential Food-Generation Surpluses and In-situ Verification, those categories which are referred as Potential Food-Generation Surpluses and In-situ Verification have been selected and they have been classified according to the stage of the agrifood chain to which it belongs:

Step Agrifood Chain	Section	Division	Group	Class	ISIC Rev. 4	
P R O D U C T I O N	SECTION A — AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FISHING	01 Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities	01,1 Growing of non-perennial crops	01.11	Growing of cereals (except rice), leguminous and oil seeds	0111
				01.12	Growing of rice	0112
				01.13	Growing of vegetables and melons, roots and tubers	0113
			01,2 Growing of perennial crops	01.14	Growing of sugar cane	0114
				01.19	Growing of other non-perennial crops	0119
				01.21	Growing of grapes	0121
				01.22	Growing of tropical and subtropical fruits	0122
		03 Fishing and aquaculture	01,4 Animal production	01.23	Growing of citrus fruits	0123
				01.24	Growing of other tree and bush fruits and nuts	0124
				01.25	Growing of other tree and bush fruits and nuts	0125
			01,5 Mixed farming	01.26	Growing of oleaginous fruits	0126
				01.27	Growing of beverage crops	0127
			01,6 Support activities to agriculture and post-harvest crop activities	01.28	Growing of spices, aromatic, drug and pharmaceutical crops	0128
				01.41	Raising of dairy cattle	0141*
01,7 Hunting, trapping and related service activities	01.42	Raising of other cattle and buffaloes	0142			
	01.43	Raising of horses and other equines	0143			
03,1 Fishing	01.44	Raising of camels and camelids	0144			
	01.45	Raising of sheep and goats	0145			
03,2 Aquaculture	01.46	Raising of swine/pigs	0146			
	01.47	Raising of poultry	0147			
03,22 Freshwater aquaculture	01.49	Raising of other animals	0149			
	01.50	Mixed farming	0150			
01,61 Support activities for crop production	01.61	Support activities for crop production	0161			
	01.62	Support activities for animal production	0162			
01,63 Post-harvest crop activities	01.63	Post-harvest crop activities	0163			
	01.70	Hunting, trapping and related service activities	0170			
10,1 Processing and preserving of meat and production of meat products	03.11	Marine fishing	0311			
	03.12	Freshwater fishing	0312			
	03.21	Marine aquaculture	0321			
	03.22	Freshwater aquaculture	0322			
10,2 Processing and preserving of fish, crustaceans and molluscs	10.11	Processing and preserving of meat	1010*			
	10.12	Processing and preserving of poultry meat	1010*			
10,13 Production of meat and poultry meat products	10.13	Production of meat and poultry meat products	1010*			
	10.20	Processing and preserving of fish, crustaceans and molluscs	1020			

Figure 5 Example of the detailed structure of economic activities with potential food-generation surpluses categorized by steps of the agrifood chain

Thus, the methodology proposes to consider the entire agrifood chain, highlighting the following main steps: **Production, Manufacturing, Distribution and Consumption**. Thanks to this categorization, it is possible to define which economic activities are potentially generators of food surpluses along the agrifood chain. Therefore, it helps to identify the group of economic activities where it is necessary to focus on the food waste quantification throughout the agrifood chain or for a specific step, according to the local legal frameworks or strategies.

Once this general framework is obtained, applicable to any municipal area within the European Union, the information is linked with the trading income tax at local level because all the entities, public and private, are connected with a particular class from NACE, identified by a specific code.

Figure 6 Theoretical approach on the methodology proposed

In this manner, thanks to the use of the GIS, it is possible to link the information on typologies classified as Potential Food-Generation Surpluses, Non-Potential Food-Generation Surpluses and In-situ Verification, with each of the entities which are part of the municipality studied.

The geographical information included in the trading income tax makes possible to create maps at local scale, where all potential focus of food surpluses generation are defined as well as their economic impact along the entire agrifood chain and classified according to the different stages.

The location of these potential focuses could define the singularity of each municipal territory regarding the food waste generation because the households are the only missing component to complete all the relevant information about the food waste situation in each municipality. However, this component can be determined without so much difficulty to estimate the food waste generation because it is possible to use the municipal census and reliable rates of food waste generation per capita.

Likewise, another way of displaying the potential focus of food surpluses generation is using a data table which provides to identify the number of entities related to the different types catalogued as Potential Food-Generation Surpluses and In-situ Verification, so that these entities are displayed and classified according to the stages of the food value. Therefore, it is possible to delimitate the entire agrifood chain related to the potential to generate food surpluses at local level.

Step Agrifood Chain	Section	Division	Group	Class	ISIC Rev. 4	Municipality 1 (Number of entities)	
P R O D U C T I O N	SECTION A — AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FISHING	01 Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities	01,1 Growing of non-perennial crops	01.11 Growing of cereals (except rice), leguminous	0111	2	
				01.12 Growing of rice	0112	1	
				01.13 Growing of vegetables and melons, roots and	0113		
				01.14 Growing of sugar cane	0114		
				01.19 Growing of other non-perennial crops	0119	1	
			01,2 Growing of perennial crops	01.21 Growing of grapes	0121		
				01.22 Growing of tropical and subtropical fruits	0122		
				01.23 Growing of citrus fruits	0123		
				01.24 Growing of some fruits and stone fruits	0124		
				01.25 Growing of other tree and bush fruits and nuts	0125		
		01,4 Animal production	01,4 Animal production	01.26 Growing of oleaginous fruits	0126		
				01.27 Growing of beverage crops	0127		
				01.28 Growing of spices, aromatic, drug and	0128		
				01.41 Raising of dairycattle	0141*		
				01.42 Raising of other cattle and buffaloes	0141*		
			01,5 Mixed farming	01,5 Mixed farming	01.43 Raising of horses and other equines	0142	
					01.44 Raising of camels and camelids	0143	
					01.45 Raising of sheep and goats	0144	1
					01.46 Raising of swine/pigs	0145	
					01.47 Raising of poultry	0146	
01,6 Support activities to agriculture and post-harvest crop activities	01,6 Support activities to agriculture and post-harvest crop activities	01.48 Raising of other animals	0148				
		01.50 Mixed farming	0150	3			
		01.61 Support activities for crop production	0161				
		01.62 Support activities for animal production	0162				
		01.63 Post-harvest crop activities	0163	1			
03 Fishing and aquaculture	01,7 Hunting, trapping and related service activities	01.70 Hunting, trapping and related service activities	0170				
		03 Fishing and aquaculture	03.1 Marine fishing	0311			
	03.12 Freshwater fishing		0312				
	03.2 Marine aquaculture		0321				
	03.22 Freshwater aquaculture		0322				
	10,1 Processing and preserving of meat and production of meat products		10,1 Processing and preserving of meat and production of meat products	10.11 Processing and preserving of meat	1010*	5	
		10.12 Processing and preserving of poultry meat		1010*	1		
10.13 Production of meat and poultry meat products		1010*		1			

Figure 7 Example of the number of entities with potential food-generation surpluses categorized by steps of the agrifood chain at local level

Furthermore, it generates a comparative framework between different municipalities thanks to the use of this methodology (Figure 8). It delimits all the economic activities likely to generate food surpluses for each stage of the agrifood chain so as to avoid remaining simply final numbers of food wastage generated and find some of the main reasons of this problem as a result of the principal economic activities that produce it and helps the decision-making process.

Section	Division	Group	Class	ISIC Rev. 4	Municipality 1	Municipality 2	
					(Number of entities)	(Number of entities)	
SECTION A — AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FISHING	01 Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities	01,1 Growing of non-perennial crops	01,11 Growing of cereals (except rice), leguminous crops and oil seeds	0111	2		
			01,12 Growing of rice	0112		3	
			01,13 Growing of vegetables and melons, roots and tubers	0113	1	1	
			01,14 Growing of sugar cane	0114			
			01,19 Growing of other non-perennial crops	0119	1		
			01,2 Growing of perennial crops	01,21 Growing of grapes	0121		
				01,22 Growing of tropical and subtropical fruits	0122		
				01,23 Growing of citrus fruits	0123		
				01,24 Growing of pome fruits and stone fruits	0124		
		01,25 Growing of other tree and bush fruits and nuts		0125			
		01,26 Growing of oleaginous fruits		0126		2	
		01,27 Growing of beverage crops		0127			
		01,28 Growing of spices, aromatic, drug and		0128			
		01,4 Animal production	01,41 Raising of dairycattle	0141*			
			01,42 Raising of other cattle and buffaloes	0141*			
			01,43 Raising of horses and other equines	0142			
			01,44 Raising of camels and camelids	0143			
			01,45 Raising of sheep and goats	0144	1	1	
			01,46 Raising of swine/pigs	0145			
			01,47 Raising of poultry	0146			
			01,49 Raising of other animals	0149			
			01,50 Mixed farming	0150	3	2	
			01,6 Support activities to agriculture and post-harvest crop activities	01,61 Support activities for crop production	0161		
01,62 Support activities for animal production	0162						
01,63 Post-harvest crop activities	0163	1					
01,7 Hunting, trapping and related service activities	01,70 Hunting, trapping and related service activities	0170					
	03 Fishing and aquaculture	03,11 Marine fishing	0311				
03,12 Freshwater fishing		0312					
03,21 Marine aquaculture		0321					
03,22 Freshwater aquaculture		0322					
10,1 Processing and preserving of meat and production of meat products	10,11 Processing and preserving of meat	1010*	5	1			
	10,12 Processing and preserving of poultry meat	1010*	1				
	10,13 Production of meat and poultry meat products	1010*	1	3			

Figure 8 Example of the comparison between two municipalities regarding the number of entities with potential food-generation surpluses categorized by steps of the agrifood chain

Results

The most relevant results thanks to the use of this methodology are obtained at local level. Obtaining all the potential focuses of food surpluses generation throughout the agrifood chain, for each and all phases, it is possible to identify all the entities susceptible to quantify the food waste situation at each of these stages, in a visual and intuitive manner. It facilitates the work of the policy-makers to establish strategies for the quantification of the food waste.

Figure 9 Case of study of the Localization of Potential Food-Generation Focus. The municipality of Zamudio (Spain)

The alternative way of display in tabular form allows the visualization of the typology of the economic activities which are potential focus of food surpluses generation and they are located in a specific municipality. In the case of study (Figures 11 and 12), the number of entities which are related to the potential food surpluses generation are shown in the municipality of Zamudio, where it is possible to appreciate its condition as an industrial city because the majority of its economic activities are located in the distribution and consumption step and very few in the production step, along the agrifood chain.

Section	Division	Group	Class	ISIC Rev. 4	Municipality of Zamudio	
SECTION A — AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FISHING	01 Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities	01,1 Growing of non-perennial crops	01,11	Growing of cereals (except rice), leguminous crops and oil seeds	0111	
			01,12	Growing of rice	0112	
			01,13	Growing of vegetables and melons, roots and tubers	0113	
			01,14	Growing of sugar cane	0114	
		01,2 Growing of perennial crops	01,21	Growing of grapes	0121	
			01,22	Growing of tropical and subtropical fruits	0122	
			01,23	Growing of citrus fruits	0123	
			01,24	Growing of pome fruits and stone fruits	0124	
			01,25	Growing of other tree and bush fruits and nuts	0125	
			01,26	Growing of oleaginous fruits	0126	
			01,27	Growing of beverage crops	0127	
			01,28	Growing of spices, aromatic, drug and pharmaceutical crops	0128	
		01,4 Animal production	01,41	Raising of dairy cattle	0141*	
			01,42	Raising of other cattle and buffaloes	0141*	
			01,43	Raising of horses and other equines	0142	
			01,44	Raising of camels and camelids	0143	
			01,45	Raising of sheep and goats	0144	
			01,46	Raising of swine/pigs	0145	
			01,47	Raising of poultry	0146	
		01,49	Raising of other animals	0149	1	
	01,5	Mixed farming	01,50	Mixed farming	0150	
	01,6 Support activities to agriculture and post-harvest crop activities	01,61	Support activities for crop production	0161		
		01,62	Support activities for animal production	0162		
01,63		Post-harvest crop activities	0163			
01,7 Hunting, trapping and related service activities	01,70	Hunting, trapping and related service activities	0170			
03 Fishing and aquaculture	03,1 Fishing	03,11	Marine fishing	0311		
		03,12	Freshwater fishing	0312		
	03,2 Aquaculture	03,21	Marine aquaculture	0321		
		03,22	Freshwater aquaculture	0322		
10,1 Processing and preserving of meat and production of meat products	10,11	Processing and preserving of meat	1010*			
	10,12	Processing and preserving of poultry meat	1010*			
	10,13	Production of meat and poultry meat products	1010*	1		
10,2 Processing and preserving of fish, crustaceans and molluscs	10,20	Processing and preserving of fish, crustaceans and molluscs	1020	1		

Figure 10 Case of study of the municipality of Zamudio. Number of entities with potential food-generation surpluses categorized by steps of the agrifood chain.

It is possible to compare with other municipalities around the European Community. In this case, it has been compared with a municipality with similar population size but with an agricultural character:

Division	Group	Class	ISIC Rev. 4	Municipality of Zamudio	Municipality of Karrantza	
01 Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities	01,1 Growing of non-perennial crops	01,11	Growing of cereals (except rice), leguminous crops and oil seeds	0111		
		01,12	Growing of rice	0112		
		01,13	Growing of vegetables and melons, roots and tubers	0113		
		01,14	Growing of sugar cane	0114		
	01,2 Growing of perennial crops	01,21	Growing of grapes	0121		
		01,22	Growing of tropical and subtropical fruits	0122		
		01,23	Growing of citrus fruits	0123		
		01,24	Growing of pome fruits and stone fruits	0124		
		01,25	Growing of other tree and bush fruits and nuts	0125	1	
		01,26	Growing of oleaginous fruits	0126		
		01,27	Growing of beverage crops	0127		
		01,28	Growing of spices, aromatic, drug and pharmaceutical crops	0128		
	01,4 Animal production	01,41	Raising of dairycattle	0141*		87
		01,42	Raising of other cattle and buffaloes	0141*		50
		01,43	Raising of horses and other equines	0142		2
		01,44	Raising of camels and camelids	0143		
		01,45	Raising of sheep and goats	0144		14
		01,46	Raising of swine/pigs	0145		
		01,47	Raising of poultry	0146		1
		01,49	Raising of other animals	0149	1	19
	01,5 Mixed farming	01,50	Mixed farming	0150		4
	01,6 Support activities to agriculture and post-harvest crop activities	01,61	Support activities for crop production	0161		1
		01,62	Support activities for animal production	0162		
01,63		Post-harvest crop activities	0163			
01,7 Hunting, trapping and related service activities	01,70	Hunting, trapping and related service activities	0170		1	
03 Fishing and aquaculture	03,1 Fishing	03,11	Marine fishing	0311		
		03,12	Freshwater fishing	0312		
	03,2 Aquaculture	03,21	Marine aquaculture	0321		
		03,22	Freshwater aquaculture	0322		
		10,11	Processing and preserving of meat	1010*	1	

Figure 11 Case of study of the comparison between the municipalities of Zamudio and Karrantza. Number of entities with potential food-generation surpluses categorized by steps of the agrifood chain.

The data analysis was also used as a basis for the definition of strategies so as to quantify the food waste at local level. This analysis can be performing through the stages within the agrifood chain as well as the different NACE categories (Sections, Divisions, Groups and Classes).

Step Agrifood Chain	Section	Division	Group	Class	ISIC Rev. 4	Municipality of Zamudio	
P R O D U C T I O N	SECTION A — AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FISHING	01 Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities	01,4 Animal production	01,49	Raising of other animals	0149	1
M A N U F A C T U R I N G	SECTION C — MANUFACTURING	10 Manufacture of food products	10,1 Processing and preserving of meat and production of meat products	10,13	Production of meat and poultry meat products	1010*	1
			10,2 Processing and preserving of fish, crustaceans and molluscs	10,20	Processing and preserving of fish, crustaceans and molluscs	1020	1
			10,5 Manufacture of dairy products	10,51	Operation of dairies and cheese making	1050*	2
			10,8 Manufacture of other food products	10,83	Processing of tea and coffee	1079*	1
		11 Manufacture of beverages	11,0 Manufacture of beverages	11,02	Manufacture of wine from grape	1102*	1
			11,0 Manufacture of beverages	11,03	Manufacture of cider and other fruit wines	1102*	1
			11,0 Manufacture of beverages	11,05	Manufacture of beer	1103*	1
				46,31	Wholesale of fruit and vegetables	4630*	1
				46,32	Wholesale of meat and meat products	4630*	4

Figure 12 Case of study of the Municipality of Zamudio. Selection of economic activities with a number of entities with potential food-generation surpluses categorized by steps of the agrifood chain.

Moreover, this methodology contributes to the detection of gaps and inconsistencies in previous studies of the food waste quantification by comparing the number of entities potentially generators of food surpluses detected, thanks to the use of this methodology, with those entities where actions of quantification of food waste were carried out. Thus, it allows checking the level of representativeness of the data of the agrifood chain at local level as well as the main steps of the value chain.

Finally, with regard to its applicability, it is worth noting that the flexibility of the methodology is not only related to different characteristics of municipalities across the European Community but it is also possible to adapt to other territorial scales, as indicated in figure 13 with the analysis of economic activities potentially generate food surpluses at regional level.

Step Agrifood Chain	Section	Division	Group	Class	ISIC Rev. 4	Basque Country	
P R O D U C T I O N	SECTION A — AGRICULTURE, FORESTRY AND FISHING	01 Crop and animal production, hunting and related service activities	01,1 Growing of non-perennial crops	01,11	Growing of cereals (except rice), leguminous crops and oil seeds	0111	521
				01,12	Growing of rice	0112	
				01,13	Growing of vegetables and melons, roots and tubers	0113	452
				01,14	Growing of sugar cane	0114	
			01,2 Growing of perennial crops	01,21	Growing of grapes	0121	694
				01,22	Growing of tropical and subtropical fruits	0122	11
				01,23	Growing of citrus fruits	0123	
				01,24	Growing of pome fruits and stone fruits	0124	53
				01,25	Growing of other tree and bush fruits and nuts	0125	10
				01,26	Growing of oleaginous fruits	0126	10
				01,27	Growing of beverage crops	0127	
				01,28	Growing of spices, aromatic, drug and pharmaceutical crops	0128	
			01,4 Animal production	01,41	Raising of dairy cattle	0141*	476
				01,42	Raising of other cattle and buffaloes	0141*	865
		01,43		Raising of horses and other equines	0142	12	
		01,44		Raising of camels and camelids	0143		
		01,45		Raising of sheep and goats	0144	440	
		01,46		Raising of swine/pigs	0145	18	
		01,47		Raising of poultry	0146	93	
		01,49	Raising of other animals	0149	386		
		01,5 Mixed farming	01,50	Mixed farming	0150	869	
		01,6 Support activities to agriculture and post-harvest crop activities	01,61	Support activities for crop production	0161	109	
			01,62	Support activities for animal production	0162	19	
		01,7 Hunting, trapping and related service activities	01,63	Post-harvest crop activities	0163	2	
			01,70	Hunting, trapping and related service activities	0170	5	
		03 Fishing and aquaculture	03,1 Fishing	03,11	Marine fishing	0311	227
				03,12	Freshwater fishing	0312	
03,2 Aquaculture	03,21		Marine aquaculture	0321	1		
	03,22		Freshwater aquaculture	0322	3		
10,1 Processing and preserving of meat and production of meat products	10,11		Processing and preserving of meat	1010*	25		
	10,12		Processing and preserving of poultry meat	1010*	3		
	10,13	Production of meat and poultry meat products	1010*	69			
10,2 Processing and preserving of fish, crustaceans and molluscs	10,20	Processing and preserving of fish, crustaceans and molluscs	1020	9			
	10,31	Processing and preserving of potatoes	1030*	5			

Figure 13 Case of study of the Basque Country (Spain). Number of entities with potential food-generation surpluses categorized by steps of the agrifood chain.

This approach would facilitate the making decision processes related to the food waste, establishing a basic framework that it is based on the economic activities which are many in numbers in relation to be potentially food surpluses generators.

Conclusions

This document sought to make a contribution proposing a new methodology for facilitating the food wastage quantification with the aim of making progress on improving the food waste knowledge and evaluating the level of reliability of the current official figures at local and supra-local scale and it allows for the development of a comparative framework between different municipalities.

Moreover, this methodology represents a step forward to identify information and data gaps about the current food waste data at different scales. Thanks to the proposed methodology is possible to specify more aspects related to the different economic activities likely to generate food surpluses. Thus, it is possible to identify the group of economic activities which are providing the current official figures at national level and at the same time it helps to detect gaps in specific activities.

Based on the identification of those gaps is possible to give priority to studies at local and regional scales to fill the existing lack of information regarding the food waste and improving the reliability of the official figures at different scales.

Furthermore, it aims to prompt thought, dialogue and constructive debate about the need for further progress in the food waste quantification at the different levels of management (local and national), particularly for searching a rigorous vision and diagnosis of the situation in order to establish a basis about where to set reduction targets in the short, medium and long term.

This report therefore emphasises the need to move towards better methodologies to quantify the food waste, using information which is already available. This would entail an effective and pragmatic way of creating a diagnosis about the food waste at local scale, but at the same time it seeks to provide a critical review to drive and lead to new quantification studies about this problem at different scales. Thus, it would avoid remaining information with possible means of improvement as official figures because these data could not be used as the basis for carrying out strategies for the current food waste reduction. That aspect represents

a fundamental step to address the problems and propose solutions or improvements of this global phenomenon which is having severe negative effects at economic, social, environmental levels as well as an important impact on social and ethical issues.

Future work

The detection of inconsistencies can also apply to the national scale, especially for those countries where the official figures are from the above-mentioned European Commission report [7], because the quantification methodology used data from animal and vegetal waste broken down into some sections, divisions, groups and classes from NACE.

Nevertheless, that methodology barely uses classes from NACE, therefore the categories employed for food waste quantification at national level encompassed not only economic activities likely to generate food surpluses but also another classes moved away from the concept of food waste generation, as well as not including classes which are susceptible to generate food waste along the agrifood chain.

Thus, using the methodology proposed is possible to detect gaps, information needs and inconsistencies within the current official figures of food waste at national level. To do this, it is necessary to compare the categories employed to prepare the national report about food wastage, with those classes likely to generate food surpluses. In this way, the current official figures could be improved in terms of information quality and showing gaps and shortcomings. Thanks to that, it would be possible to provide a more comprehensive idea of their adequacy to serve as a baseline or it is necessary to promote further initiatives in the area of the food waste quantification at national scale.

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